

A training workbench based on transient building models for creating intelligent energy operators

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Abstract

The development of intelligent control-oriented solutions for building energy systems is a promising research field. The development of effective systems relies on seldom available large data sets or on simulation environments, either for training or execution phases. The creation of simulation environments based on thermal models is a challenging task, requiring the usage of third-party solutions and high levels of expertise in the energy engineering field, which poses relevant restrictions to the development of control-oriented research.

In this work, a training workbench is presented, integrating an accurate but lightweight lumped capacitance model with proven accuracy to represent the thermal dynamics of buildings, engineering models for energy systems in buildings, and user behavior models into an overall building energy performance forecasting model. It is developed in such a way that it can be easily integrated into control-oriented applications, with no requirements to use complex, third-party tools.

Impact Statement

The presented research introduces a novel training workbench for developing intelligent energy operators by integrating lumped capacitance models. By eliminating the need for complex third-party tools to connect operators with traditional simulation models, the workbench simplifies the development and implementation of controllers. This advancement holds significant potential for enhancing building energy efficiency, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and supporting sustainable development in the built environment.

1. Introduction

Energy use in buildings is known to be the source of up to 40% of all greenhouse gas emissions (IEA, 2019). Among other measures, improvements in control systems for heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) are known to be a relevant source of performance improvement (Fernandez et al., 2017).

Research in this field seeks to implement automatic decision-making processes that will try to optimize the operation of existing HVAC systems so that the same comfort levels are achieved with lower energy

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usage. In this regard, different solutions have been implemented, such as model predictive controls (MPCs), expert rule-based systems (ERSs), and machine learning (ML) algorithms. Recent research reveals that ML algorithms are gaining popularity because they are giving valid results in terms of energy performance, without the requirement of deep expert knowledge in the energy field (Wei et al., 2018).

However, practical implementations of MPC and ML algorithms require several data streams, which is not possible in real scenarios. Instead, simulation environments (Mason and Grijalva, 2019; Fu et al., 2022) are used to generate all possible use cases that may appear in the target environment. For example, an implementation of reinforcement learning (RL) (Sutton and Barto, 2018) agent, as one of the ML paradigms, would need several years of data from an environment to be trained (Nagy et al., 2023). Using a simulation environment, the acquisition of valid knowledge becomes feasible as it can provide all possible situations that may occur.

Controllers are expected to optimize building performance based on their expectations (MPC and ERS) or learnings (RL) on building performance. When using simulation models to gain this knowledge, it is essential that the models are reliable and accurate. Indeed, variations in controller performance caused by model accuracy have been documented (Guo et al., 2024). Considering the exposure of building performance to climate and usage, these interactions should be modeled with particular care. Model creation is known to require extensive use of experienced engineers (Blum et al., 2022), typically ad hoc, developed for each building (Nagy et al., 2023). This is difficult and/or cost-inefficient.

In the current state of the art, various works utilize simulation and cosimulation environments to train controllers (Zhang et al., 2021). However, most of the proposed models are relatively simple (Zhang et al., 2019) and their quality is only partially assessed, typically using metrics such as the yearly mean absolute prediction error. Besides, there is often insufficient evaluation of model performance concerning transient behavior and key input–output relationships, such as occupancy (Wang et al., 2021). Consequently, there is a significant risk that the performance of these simulation environments may not accurately reflect the transient performance of the target environment in real buildings.

Regardless of the accuracy of the simulation environment, setting up such a system is a complex task involving cross-domain expertise in the fields of mechanical engineering, energy modeling, control systems, and software engineering, as well as expert-level capacities in one or several building energy simulation tools and cosimulation environments. These result in substantial entry barriers to the research, development, and implementation of smart control-oriented solutions for buildings.

Considering the aforementioned issues, a simple simulation environment is proposed, incorporating (1) a calibrated model of a building with an embedded HVAC system and (2) a realistic occupational model based on Markov chains.

This environment has been created to ensure ease of use for the development of MPC controllers and ML agents for building energy control. Additionally, the re-utilization and extension of this environment are possible by integrating it with model structures and automated model calibration approaches, such as those developed in Leprince et al. (2022a), (2022b). Furthermore, this environment is scalable to model much larger contexts, such as large multi-zone buildings and pools of buildings within district heating systems.

The main contribution of this work is the development of a novel technical engine that simplifies the implementation of model structures to create intelligent energy operators. Unlike existing approaches, this work eliminates the need for any “connector” or “middleware” applications, enabling direct interaction between the developed agent and the simulation environment. Additionally, it removes the necessity of using third-party software engines to simulate the target environment. This advancement allows for more streamlined and efficient integration, reducing complexity and potential points of failure, thereby significantly enhancing the robustness and performance of intelligent energy systems.

The article is structured in the following sections. **Section 2** will describe the state of the art, in which the description of the current models used and how they are implemented will be explained. **Section 3** will explain the thermal model used in the presented work. **Section 4** will describe the technical solution used to exploit the presented model and will explain how to change it to adapt it to any other model. **Section 5**

will validate the presented implementation and the model used. [Section 6](#) will discuss why the presented approach is useful for researchers and what the key differences are against other approaches. [Section 7](#) will expose the possible technical extensions and model extensions of the presented work. Finally, [Section 8](#) will conclude the manuscript.

2. State of the art

In this section, we perform a revision on the simulation environments oriented for the control of building energy systems, considering the modeling approach of the physical system ([Section 2.1](#)) and the informatics tools and processes required to implement such models ([Section 2.2](#)).

2.1. Modeling approach

Building energy models (BEMs) are most commonly classified in relation to their construction based on physical or data-driven approaches. Approaches based on explicit physical relations are commonly defined as “white-box” (WB) models, while purely data-driven models are named “black-box” (BB) models. In between these, semi-physical models or “gray-box” (GB) models are placed. Each one has its own advantages and caveats depending on the particular application.

WB models are built based on the explicit formulation of energy flows and balances in buildings. Complex models are built based on the aggregation of a large number of equations, each of which models a small subset of the energy system. With initial developments more than 50 years ago, WB models have grown in complexity and scale, and several simulation tools, such as Energy Plus (National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), 2017), TRNSYS (University of Wisconsin—Madison Solar Energy Laboratory, 1975), ESPr (University of Strathclyde. Energy Systems Research Unit, 2002), and so forth, are accepted by the Building Energy Simulation community, mostly for their use in the design of new buildings. In recent years, specific libraries (Lawrence Berkley National Laboratory, 1998) for the general-purpose Modelica language (Modelica Association, 1997) have also gained popularity, particularly for HVAC and control applications.

One of the advantages of WB models is that they are built based on design data and do not require historical data to develop the model. This is in line with their main applications as support tools for building designers but poses problems as there is a frequently documented energy “performance gap” (Johnston et al., 2015; Zou et al., 2018) from the design to the post-construction phase. This gap is typically in the range of a factor of 2.

Although not originally designed for this purpose, WB models have also been used as simulation environments for building control applications. Energy Plus is commonly used as a unique simulator (Kwak et al., 2015; Jia et al., 2019; Brandi et al., 2020; Coraci et al., 2023, 2024) or as part of larger cosimulation environments (Cucca and Ianakiev, 2020; Brandi et al., 2022). This software is also used when scaling up simulation environments to deal with city-scale applications (Pinto et al., 2021a; Pinto et al., 2021b), which, in some cases, require developing surrogate models (Pinto et al., 2021a). In many cases, several WB models are integrated into a cosimulation environment, where EnergyPlus is the core tool for building physics, and other systems are incorporated for building occupancy (Naspi et al., 2018; Jia and Srinivasan, 2020) and HVAC modeling (Cucca and Ianakiev, 2020). Here, cosimulation environments and tools to embed WB models as functional mockup units (Lawrence Berkley National Laboratory, 2019) have substantially facilitated the integration of WB models among them and with other general-purpose programming languages.

Modelica is typically the most used tool for the modeling of HVAC and controls, sometimes also performing the (simplified) modeling of buildings (Guo et al., 2024) or by building cosimulation environments with EnergyPlus (Cucca and Ianakiev, 2020). Although the main trend is to use the above-mentioned tools, similar approaches have been used to integrate other models, such as IES Virtual Environment (IESVE) (Naspi et al., 2018), or to couple models with real-life pieces of equipment under hardware-in-the-loop (Calfa et al., 2023) approaches.

The power of WB models resides in the capacity to create virtual models of any building and energy system based only on information already available during the preliminary design stage of buildings. Although this has made it popular for the development of simulation environments for research purposes, in most research works, the quality of the simulation environment has not been checked against real building performance data (Mason and Grijalva, 2019) or accuracy has been validated only at aggregated levels, which provides potential limitations to the performance and applicability of control applications investigated on top of them.

Fully opposed to WB, BB models do not require knowledge of the configuration of the physical system and are built only based on historical data of input and output variables of the environment (building) to be modeled.

BB models are used by authors when WB or GB models cannot be used due to the absence of engineering information or large scale of integrated phenomena, for example, for the estimation of energy loads of a District Heating (DH). Lumbreras et al. (2022) present a procedure in which a heat load prediction model in buildings is performed based on data from smart meters with hourly resolution. By applying a set of different statistical procedures (interquartile range filtering criteria, remove nonvalid values, etc.) for preprocessing data sources, doing an extensive data analysis (detection of different heating patterns in different buildings and time periods) and training different ML algorithms (decision trees and multivariate regressions) authors created a valid general dataset that contains historical energy usage patterns that are used to feed a relatively simple model with no prior knowledge of the building.

In Lopez-Villamor et al. (2024), the authors present a methodology to create a BB model that can be used to train autoregressive models to predict thermal loads in commercial buildings and optimize their thermal consumption. A set of historical weather data, occupancy information, and indoor set point temperatures are used to develop individual predictions for 168 data clusters, each representing one individual time of the week. Each cluster is used to train an independent autoregressive exogenous sub-model to calibrate the BB model. The model is validated using a typical k -fold cross-validation procedure, and it is compared against other models with a lesser complexity.

Liang et al. (2023) present a unified framework for endowing BB models with rejection ability. Authors explain that the obtained data for creating a BB model may not be useful if the collected data for creating it are limited to certain operational conditions or outside the scope of training data. For that reason, the rejection methodology rejects the possible outcomes that are not reliable for being used in a prediction methodology, ensuring that the created BB model is going to be more precise for developing control-oriented applications.

The accuracy of these models is highly reliant on the amount and quality of the data. Previous works have showcased the relevance of social behavior (Zhan et al., 2020; Lumbreras et al., 2023) and climate patterns (Lumbreras et al., 2023; Borgato et al., 2024; Hajri et al., 2024) as key information leading to different energy performances of buildings. Thus, data availability should be properly balanced to develop BB models suitable for modeling energy performance for all this variability.

A key issue when developing a BB model for control application is that observations should properly represent the variation not only of model disturbances (climate, occupancy, etc.) but also of control inputs to the system (i.e., temperature set points, activation of fans, etc.). This last item is commonly difficult to achieve, as historical observations are commonly biased due to the existing operational criteria (i.e., fixed set-points and operational schedules).

GB models are between the previous approaches (Li et al., 2021). A reduced set of formulas with physical correspondence is defined, and its parameters are calibrated with operational data. With this approach, GB models integrate the best of WB and BB models as they are physically significant and fit the data at the same time. GB models are reduced-order models that capture the main dynamics of buildings, where the resulting performance of many energy transfer paths is formulated. Reference works in building physics model building performance in equations (Bacher and Madsen, 2011; Wang et al., 2019), and procedures have been developed to identify model structures and calibrate parameters automatically (Leprince et al., 2022a; Leprince et al., 2022b), as well as integration into building control systems (De Coninck et al., 2016; Blum et al., 2022).

In most cases, GB models are represented by using a Resistance-Capacitance (RC) structure, where resistance represents energy transfer and capacitance represents energy storage. Recent identification processes driven by statistical significance show that models with 2–3 capacitances are suitable to represent the heat dynamics in buildings (Leprince et al., 2022a).

Although GB models are suitable for energy performance modeling, they are most focused on the performance of the structural components in buildings and do not typically consider the interaction with HVAC systems and social behavior associated with building occupants and their associated loads (i.e., lighting). With some complex exceptions (De Coninck and Helsen, 2016; Blum et al., 2022), these are either left out of the models or integrated in a very simplistic manner.

In this work, we take advantage of the simplicity of GB models to create the basis for building energy performance simulators. We complement the GB model with specific additions to integrate HVAC and occupancy modeling.

There is an underlying discussion on the time and expertise required to build a suitable energy model, where WB and GB models are commonly attributed to require greater efforts in this process, but this has been substantially reduced in recent times by means of automated WB model generation procedures and automated GB model identification and calibration techniques. In our case, we trust that already stable models such as (Bacher and Madsen, 2011) can be directly used in our environment, and model calibration approaches such as those developed in (Leprince et al., 2022a; Leprince et al., 2022b) will be able to generate models for other buildings in an efficient way.

2.2. Implementation

Intelligent energy operators are commonly implemented by using informatics tools. These tools try to mimic human behavior by doing intelligent decision-making processes in which the data from the environment is understood and suitable actions are executed. However, to be able to implement these processes (commonly named intelligent agents), valid data from the target environment and the installed building active system should be provided. Thus, researchers could use the information from the developed physical models to use them as the backbone of their technical implementations. The models will play a critical role in the creation of these agents because they will be able to provide solid and valid data to fit the decisions of the agent according to the current conditions of the target environment.

Depending on the physical model approach (WB, GB, and BB) and the informatics programming language (Java, Python, C, etc.) used, different technical tools and architectures should be considered.

WB-based solutions are developed by using third-party applications (simulation tools such as EnergyPlus or Modelica). This implies that a logical connection between the model and the technical implementation is required. The most common approach is usually performing a cosimulation, where the logical code is written and connected with the simulation environment. There is a need to develop/parametrize a custom model within the simulation environment (a quite expert task) or rely on predefined configurations.

Simulation tools are commonly written in C or C++. Considering the preeminence of Python as a programming language in the scientific community, authors have tried to create “bridges” to train their control-oriented implementations.

For example, Sinergym (Campoy-Nieves et al., 2025) is a Python library allowing a direct connection with Energy Plus to develop RL algorithms by using the Gymnasium library (Towers et al., 2024) and interact at each time step. On each RL episode, a new EnergyPlus instance is created, and interaction is performed until the episode finishes. Sinergym has drawbacks linked to the complexity of installation and configuration of the system. Although a Docker image is supplied, there is still a need to install several additional components. Additionally, the training procedure is computationally intensive due to the need to execute several instances of EnergyPlus.

ALFALFA¹ is a web-based application for running WB models from different simulation engines (EnergyPlus, Modelica, etc.) that allows uploading custom models using a web-based interface or Python

¹ <https://github.com/NREL/alfalfa/wiki>.

programming code and executing these with various configurations (e.g., simulation start time, simulation end time, etc.). The configuration of “external clock” allows defining how the model advances in time through a “Stepping manner,” which is an important feature for ML developments. It also allows for modifying model input points by using a Python dictionary (e.g., set a value of an outside air damper to 0.7 from the original Energy Plus model). ALFALFA requires that a full server–client architecture is deployed, a specific format is used (Open Studio Workflow, OSW) with its own format and file configuration, and that manual efforts are performed to connect simulations with developments.

BOPTTEST (Blum et al., 2021) is a framework with many similarities to ALFALFA, but a more generalized purpose system to focus on benchmarking building control performance over pre-defined scenarios. The main difference between BOPTTEST and ALFALFA is that the former is focused only on testing scenarios, and the latter is focused on training and testing scenarios. Despite being a good tool for rapid-testing purposes, it has the same problems as ALFALFA and does not provide options to customize training or processes or customize BEMs outside the provided repository of test cases.

Advanced Controls Test Bed (ACTB)² is presented as a middle solution between BOPTTEST and ALFALFA. ACTB develops a “high-fidelity” model by coupling building envelope and load modeling (EnergyPlus) with HVAC models and controls (Modelica). Interfaces are provided for developing MPC or RL controls. Although the software is complete in terms of modeling and control execution, the usage becomes more complicated than the previously presented systems, as two independent simulation tools need to be configured. Also, this environment is in early development stages.

The previously analyzed frameworks were used in several contributions. For example, Manjavacas et al. (2024) used the Sinergym library to compare the performance of different RL implementations with various buildings and climate conditions.

Kang et al. (2024) utilized ALFALFA to create a Building Operations Emulator system to allow Building BEMs to control the building elements as if they were controlling them in a real scenario. A bridge from ALFALFA is used to obtain the data points of the BACnet standard protocol and allow the direct interaction between a BEM and a virtual building. They demonstrate the potential to obtain realistic responses from virtual buildings to train control-oriented applications.

Yang et al. (2020) used BOPTTEST tool to evaluate an MPC controller where a Modelica model was used to simulate electric loads and thermal dynamics of a building and its HVAC system, and which factors affect the performance of the proposed MPC.

Dey et al. (2023) used ACTB to test two RL algorithms against a rule-based controller in a multi-zone building energy simulation. The authors reported the necessity of using a specific connector to effectively connect their RL implementation with the simulation environment.

GB models are directly integrated with the existing code. After having developed the model, the representative model equations are directly written in the programming language used as a set of functions or methods. These functions will be called by the logical programming pipeline, considering the detected input variables such as time, weather, electricity prices, and so on. The results of the methods will be the evolution of the thermal behavior of the building and its associated costs.

The authors in Talib et al. (2023) perform an experimentation in which a GB model based on a RC-network is compared against a BB model based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). To create each model, the authors used experimental data from the research building in Oak Ridge National Laboratory. In the case of RC-Network, the authors built it using first-order ordinary differential equations, considering the heat transfer equations of a 3R2C-based thermal network of the zone using a state-space formulation. The ANN network was built directly by taking measured historical raw data from building sensors from September 20 to September 28 of 2019, and applying different statistical procedures to feed ANN networks (Pearson correlation, data reshaping, etc.). According to the authors, both models used the same number of input parameters to perform a fair comparison (although ANN models require fewer input parameters). Results reveal that the GB model outperforms the ANN model in terms of accuracy and

² <https://github.com/henze-research-group/MODRLC>.

prediction stability. However, the authors explain that the performance of ANN models could be improved by executing a hyperparameter optimization procedure, a feature engineering process, an ensemble method, and weight initialization.

Other authors (Kumar et al., 2023) create an ANN and an RC model to enhance the usage of an MPC-based controller. The RC network is created as a data source for estimating how the thermal environment changes over time, and the ANN is created to add thermal disturbances to the model to create a more realistic environment. To create the RC model, the authors used data from the target environment (a total of 1 week of data measurements of 1 min). To create the ANN, the authors used 20 weeks of data. To compare the performance of their solution, the authors compare different MPC solutions with and without the ANN-based thermal disturbance estimator and the RC model estimations. Results reveal that the usage of their ANN thermal disturbance and the RC network model estimations result in an accurate and optimized MPC controller against others.

Abtahi et al. (2024) present a manuscript in which they used a Control-Oriented Archetype Model (Candanedo et al., 2022) as a GB model to represent the zone/building environment with the aim of building an online economic MPC (E-MPC) to simulate optimal heating load management. The case study was applied in a research house (Hydro-Québec) using an 11R6C network. To compare the results of the developed solutions, the authors compared the actual indoor temperature versus a 24 h-ahead predictions done by their CAM implementation. Results revealed that near-term predictions are more accurate than the long-term ones, and that the energy savings on those near-term predictions were around 30% of reduction in daily heating cost compared to the reference operation.

Gokhale et al. (2022) present an implementation of a Physics Informed Neuronal Networks (PINNs). The primary objective is to develop a prediction network that forecasts room temperature and power consumption for subsequent time steps in a target building. This network will consider a set of input variables, despite the absence of information about certain environmental elements, such as solar radiation and other factors. Thus, the aim is to build a PINN that can estimate the hidden states of the environment and provide accurate values. To build the PINN, the authors used an RC model to define the loss function and the optimization strategy of the ANN. To validate it, the authors used two approaches: (1) a synthetic validation dataset and (2) real-world data obtained from a cold storage unit. Results showed that the two developed PINNs provide good prediction rates with an error rate <0.25 °C.

BB models are commonly implemented by loading raw data from the target model in the implementation, which alleviates the requirement of having prior knowledge of the building to build a thermal model. However, the data obtained from these sensors should be used carefully to select only the most meaningful values, ensuring the trustworthiness of the final implementation. As explained in GB models, these models could also be directly integrated with the existing programming language. However, certain operations to load and adjust the data should be done, for example, load data from an Excel file or plain text, delete nonvalid values, and so on.

Taking into account the aforementioned lines, Knudsen et al. (2021) used a test facility located at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology to adjust the water flow of a hydronic radiator to optimize its usage. To do it, a novel low-cost E-MPC controller was created by using a BB-based model. The model was created by changing the set point of the building from 21 to 24 °C. The E-MPC model was trained with 14 days of model data and tested with 4 days of the same model. Results showed that their E-MPC controllers consumed 1.3% more energy than a constant setpoint baseline of 21 °C but reduced the energy costs by 22.5%.

Lin et al. (2022) build a computational fluid dynamics model using the software 6SigmaDC to create an experimental platform that provides data from the tool to emulate the cooling state of a data center room with different installed racks (20 racks arranged in 4 rows). The emulated environment creates data from two different scenarios: (1) when the computer room reaches a thermal equilibrium (specific workload configuration and air conditioning parameter settings) and (2) when the computer room is in a transient scenario because there are dynamic changes in its parameters (dynamic change of parameter settings to predict the future system state). The aim is to apply and compare the performance of ML models to estimate the temperature predictions based on the possible workloads of their servers to adjust the installed

cooling system and save energy. Results demonstrated that XGBoost (an extreme gradient boosting tree algorithm) and LightGBM (a gradient boosting framework for using tree-based learning algorithms) are superior to others (ANNs, Support Vector Machines, etc.) in prediction accuracy and computational overhead.

Kamel et al. (2020) studied what are the most meaningful inputs that are required for forecasting energy consumption in residential buildings (cooling load, heating load, hot water, and ventilation fan). To perform the study, the authors used a tool to generate synthetic data based on a program called the Building Energy Optimization Tool, which is developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory. The overall idea is to generate a dataset to emulate a BB modeling approach, which will be cleaned and curated in different ways using classical statistics techniques (e.g., Pearson correlation) to apply a regression algorithm to compute its root mean square error to determine which process is the best for determining the most interesting inputs that could be used for forecasting the energy consumption.

In Mugnini et al. (2020), the authors compared GB (RC-network) versus BB (data-driven) models with the aim of comparing what is the real performance of a simple MPC controller designed to minimize the total energy cost while ensuring that the demand satisfaction is guaranteed. To do this, an MPC controller was designed using MATLAB, and it is fed with the data coming from both models. The BB model was created from a set of datasets generated by a TRNSYS model, and the GB model is modeled according to the target building. Results showed that, unless the performance of both approaches is similar, the GB approach is better because it follows the system dynamics more accurately than the BB. The BB model implementation exceeds the upper comfort limit by 1°; thus, it seems that a small error in prediction leads to excessive temperature inside the building.

3. Thermal model

The dynamic thermal system simulator is built based on a set of independent models. A validated Building Physics model is used as the root model, and its modeling capacity is extended with regards to ventilation systems, heat distribution and diffusion systems, heat production systems, power balance in the heating system, as well as internal heat gains and occupancy. Altogether, the model is able to characterize the transient energy performance of a building and its energy systems, considering its interactions with climate and complex user behavior.

3.1. Building physics model

Building physics (heat transfer, thermal inertia, etc.) is simulated through a lumped capacitance model grouping the effective thermal inertia of the system into several discrete lumps (Vivian et al., 2017). This model is a representation of the heat transfer dynamics of an Full Physical System (FPS). A validated state-space model of a building is taken from (Bacher and Madsen, 2011). The selected model (referenced as *TiTmTeThTsAeRia*) consists of a reduced set of equations modeling the heat dynamics of the building. These deal with heat transfer through the building envelope, the impact of solar radiation, and thermal mass in the building, as well as short-term dynamics associated with the sensors. A basic heat input model is also presented. According to the authors' statement, the proposed model and parameter identification techniques are suitable for control applications. The model has been properly validated by the authors and is considered suitable to characterize the interaction of the building with local climate.

The dynamics of the building are linked to four states as defined in Equations (3.1)–(3.4) (the nomenclature is described in Appendix A on Table A1). These equations are adapted from Equations (13)–(28) from Bacher and Madsen (2011), considering only relevant parameters in the *TiTmTeThTsAeRia* model. Stochastic terms are disregarded as they are only required in the identification process.

$$\frac{dT_s}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_s} \cdot \frac{(T_i - T_s)}{R_s} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\frac{dT_h}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_h} \cdot \left[\frac{(T_i - T_h)}{R_{ih}} + Q_h \right] \quad (3.2)$$

$$\frac{dT_i}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_i} \cdot \left[\frac{(T_s - T_i)}{R_s} + \frac{(T_h - T_i)}{R_{ih}} + \frac{(T_e - T_i)}{R_{ie}} + A_w \cdot I_s \right] \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{dT_e}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_e} \cdot \left[\frac{(T_i - T_e)}{R_{ie}} + \frac{(T_a - T_e)}{R_{ea}} + A_e \cdot I_s \right] \quad (3.4)$$

The parameters in the model are associated with a 120 m² single-story building located in Denmark, but the methodology defined in this work allows getting equivalent parameters for other buildings of interest. The application of this model for control-oriented applications requires its extension to incorporate key systems and phenomena not included in the original model, such as building ventilation, occupancy, and heat production and distribution systems.

3.2. Extensions of the model

3.2.1. Ventilation

Despite ventilation being mandatory according to most modern building regulations, it is not explicitly considered in the original model. An additional energy flow is added to Equation (3.4) based on ventilation rates defined by the American Society of Heating (2015). A fixed ventilation rate is taken, considering the most limiting factor among the maximum occupation rates or floor area-based occupation rates. The effective energy flow is determined according to Equation (3.5), which is then converted into an effective thermal resistance in Equation (3.6). Accordingly, Equation (3.3) is replaced with Equation (3.7).

$$Q_{vent} = 1.21 \cdot V_{vent} \cdot (T_a - T_i) \quad (3.5)$$

$$R_{vent} = \frac{1}{1.21 \cdot V_{vent}} \quad (3.6)$$

$$\frac{dT_i}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_i} \cdot \left[\frac{(T_s - T_i)}{R_s} + \frac{(T_h - T_i)}{R_{ih}} + \frac{(T_e - T_i)}{R_{ie}} + A_w \cdot I_s + \frac{(T_a - T_i)}{R_{vent}} \right] \quad (3.7)$$

3.2.2. Heat distribution and diffusion system

The model presented in Equations (3.1)–(3.4) is based on electric heaters, where no physical limitation is introduced to the diffusion capacity of the heating system. This approach is in line with the focus of Bacher and Madsen (2011) on the modeling of the heat dynamics of the building. However, modification is necessary to allow the description and manipulation of real heating systems. An exponential equation for radiator systems in Truschel (2002) is adopted as per Equation (3.8).

$$Q_h = Q_{h,nom} \cdot \left[\frac{(T_{sup,effect} - T_i)}{(T_{sup,design} - T_{i,design})} \right]^n \quad (3.8)$$

3.2.3. Heat production technology

A typical configuration of heat pumps is assumed (Equations [3.9] to [3.12]), in which the thermodynamic heating cycle is operated whenever the required heating power (Q_h) is within the heating capacity of the heat pump ($Q_{hp,max}$). During peak periods, in-line heaters are used to boost heat production for the remaining required energy ($Q_{h,boost}$).

$$Q_{h,hp} = \min(Q_h, Q_{hp,max}) \quad (3.9)$$

$$Q_{h,boost} = \max(Q_h - Q_{h,hp}, Q_{boost,max}) \quad (3.10)$$

$$COP = 2.60 + 0.0465 \cdot T_a - 0.0187 \cdot T_{sup,effect} \quad (3.11)$$

$$P_{h,el} = \frac{Q_{h,hp}}{COP} + Q_{h,boost} \quad (3.12)$$

Equation (3.11) is formulated in accordance with De Coninck and Helsen (2016), where empirical correlations of two air–water heat pumps are presented. Coefficients of both heat pumps have been averaged, and only significant terms have been considered. Considering typical operational controls in heat pump systems, these are not activated until relevant heating loads are required. This is due to low performance and high wear in those conditions. For this reason, a minimum heat load of $Q_{hp,min}$ is defined. For heat loads below this threshold, no heating is provided.

3.2.4. Power balance in the heating system

There is a need to perform an energy balance of heat production and diffusion systems, achieved by adapting the effective supply temperature to the physical constraints of the system. The heat delivery capacity of the system is calculated for the supply temperature set by the controller ($T_{sup,effect} = T_{sup,set}$) and compared with the actual capacity of the heat production system. If the delivery capacity exceeds the heat production capacity, then an effective supply temperature is calculated ($T_{sup,effect} < T_{sup,set}$) with Equation (3.10) so that the energy balance in Equation (3.13) is ensured.

$$Q_h = Q_{hp,max} + Q_{boost,max} \quad (3.13)$$

3.2.5. Internal heat gains and occupancy model

An occupancy model is defined based on a mathematical algorithm by Page et al. (2008) using Markov chains (Feller, 1968) to generate occupant patterns based on the probability distribution of the target place. The model generates time series of zeros (absence) and ones (presence), reproducing arrivals and departures of the target place and alternating short periods of presence and absence. In this regard, the algorithm takes a monthly and an hourly presence probability distribution to generate occupant patterns. For this implementation, a common office occupation probability pattern with a maximum occupancy of 12 persons has been adopted to create stochastic vectors of 2-year occupation data in hourly intervals. The heat load associated with occupancy (Equation [3.14]) is calculated based on well-grounded engineering calculations (ASHRAE American Society of Heating Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers, 2017) assuming a metabolic rate of 77 W/m^2 for male occupants and 54 W/m^2 for female occupants and a surface area of 1.8 m^2 per occupant, resulting in a specific heat load factor (F_{ihg}) of 117.81 W/pers .

$$Q_{ig} = F_{ihg} \cdot Occup \quad (3.14)$$

3.3. Input/output variables

Measured climate data and reliable energy costs are obtained to build a realistic scenario for using the model. Climate data to feed the air temperature (T_a) and global radiance (I_s) in the provided equations were extracted from local climate stations placed next to the used model. The obtained data has a time resolution of 1 min and corresponds to 2017 and 2019.

For energy data, historical electricity prices have been obtained through a local power exchange company. Hourly electricity prices in EUR/kWh from 2017 to 2019 have been used to calculate the total cost of activating the heat pump by multiplying these costs with the electrical power ($P_{h,el}$) obtained through Equation (3.12). The HVAC system is controlled with three signals activating the heating system

(ACT_H), activating the ventilation system (ACT_{vent}), and setting the supply temperature to the radiator system ($T_{sup,set}$).

4. Software description

In this section, a description of the technical architecture of the training workbench is provided. The aim is to understand what the logic of the presented approach is, how it is working, and how it can be modified to adjust it for creating new custom solutions.

4.1. Architecture description

Figure 1 depicts the following architecture for creating the simulation environment. It is mainly composed of two modules: (1) the data extraction and model definition module (right section), and (2) the simulation engine and the data endpoints (left section).

The end user uses the Representational State Transfer (REST) application as an access point to the simulation tool to send the required information to start a simulation procedure. The simulation engine acts as a “middle” connector between Application Programming Interface (API) endpoints and the simulation core and executes the required code to perform the simulation process. The simulation engine executes the model formulas and adds the required exogenous and occupant estimator values to the model. Results are sent to the end user once the simulation procedure is completed.

4.1.1. Data extraction and model definition

The data extraction and model definition module comprised different libraries to extract data from trusted data sources, allowing the definition of custom model formulas. This module is composed of three main

Figure 1. General overview of the architecture. At the right, the data extraction and model formulas; at the left, and the simulation engine and data endpoints.

components: (1) the exogenous data feed; (2) the occupant estimator generator; (3) the *GB* model equations.

The **exogenous data** component consists of a set of programming code files and data loading libraries to externally load data from different data sources (*.csv, *.xml, databases, etc.). The component aims to manage exogenous or *uncontrollable data*, that is, data that cannot be easily modeled due to its invariant nature (weather conditions, electricity prices, etc.), to feed thermal model equations. In the presented implementation, climate and energy data sources were considered as exogenous data.

The **occupant estimator** component described in Section 3.2 contains the required code to generate an hourly vector for each simulated year; thus, the shape of the created vector is $[1, n]$ where n is the total yearly hours to simulate. The resulting occupant vector is pseudo-randomized (following the probability boundaries of the original algorithm); hence, every time the algorithm is executed, a random pattern of occupant estimation is given. The data from the resulting vector is managed by the simulation engine module to be used directly in the model equations to calculate the building internal gains. The reason for creating this module instead of using a prediction algorithm or historical data from a building is that the former requires large quantities of historical occupation data, and the latter does not allow the creation of unpredictable situations, for example, a pandemic situation.

The **model formulas** component contains the GB-based formulas described in Section 3. This model is divided into four different files: (1) **costs** with the aim of calculating the operational cost of the active element to be controlled; (2) **equations** to calculate the **thermal behavior** of the building; (3) **radiator heat pump** calculating the hydronic behavior of the radiators, heat production, and internal gains; (4) **ventilation** which plugs the thermal variations produced by a ventilation system.

4.1.2. Simulation engine and data endpoints

The simulation engine and data extraction endpoints module comprise the software components required to create a simulation environment and allow third parties to use the simulation data to train and evaluate their algorithms. This module uses and manages the different components presented in Section 4.1.1 and acts as a middleware communication channel between these components and requests from different implementations. As depicted previously in Figure 1, the module is divided into two different components: (1) the simulator engine and (2) the REST application service.

The **simulator engine** allows for interactive simulation of the behavior of a building when an active element is used (e.g., an HVAC system). The code is composed of one class that allows defining how to load the different data sources (exogenous data, occupants, model formulas, etc.) and other additional configurations such as the Δ time gap between iterations or the total simulation time. The simulator engine aims at supporting a decision-making process; thus, each iteration represents a simulated time iteration (t) in the equations in Section 3 (each iteration satisfies the time difference parameter dt). Hence, on each interaction, values are calculated using the previously calculated results and a Δ time.

By default, the Δ time is set to 10 s and the starting thermal values (T_e , T_s , and T_r) are set to 20.0 °C, but it is possible to adjust these values via class instance parameters. In addition, it is possible to configure the total simulation time. By default, the system provides a yearly simulation from January 1 of the initial year to December 31 of the final year, but it is possible to configure the final date by giving it in a year–month–day format. The maximum time steps to be simulated are calculated by taking the time difference (δ) between the initial and final dates, and the defined Δ time gap (dt).

Algorithm 1 shows a pseudo-code to illustrate the logic followed by the simulator engine. As illustrated, the code loads the required exogenous data and initializes the required values to calculate the operational costs (C_{op}), the building internal gains (Q_{ig}), and the variation of the thermal values of the

building (dT_s , dT_h , dT_i , and dT_e) when an installed HVAC device is powered on or off (ACT_{HP}). The decision to activate or not to activate the HVAC device (ACT_{HP}) is decided by the researcher's algorithm.

Algorithm 1. *Simulation engine logical execution.*

```

1:  $\Delta \leftarrow 10$  ◁ In seconds
2:  $t_{max} \leftarrow \text{max\_timesteps}$  ◁ Total yearly simulation
3:  $\text{exogenous} \leftarrow \text{exogenous\_data}$ .
4:  $O \leftarrow \text{generated\_occupant\_estimation}$ .
5:  $T_s, T_h, T_i, T_e \leftarrow 20$  ◁ Degree Celsius
6: for  $t = 1, 2, \dots, t_{max}$  do.
7:    $\text{electricity\_price}, T_a \leftarrow \text{exogenous}_t$ 
8:    $Q_h, P_{el} \leftarrow \text{calculate\_cop}(ACT_{HP}, T_i, T_a)$ 
9:    $C_{op} \leftarrow \text{calculate\_costs}(P_{el}, \text{electricity\_price})$ 
10:   $Q_{ig} \leftarrow \text{calculate\_internal\_gain}(O_t)$ 
11:   $Q_{vent} \leftarrow \text{calculate\_vent\_resistance}(T_a, T_i)$ 
12:   $dT_s \leftarrow \text{calculate\_t\_s}(\Delta, T_i, T_s)$ 
13:   $dT_h \leftarrow \text{calculate\_t\_h}(\Delta, Q_h, T_i, T_h)$ 
14:   $dT_i \leftarrow \text{calculate\_t\_i}(\Delta, Q_{ig}, T_s, T_i, T_h, T_e, Q_{vent})$ 
15:   $dT_e \leftarrow \text{calculate\_t\_e}(\Delta, T_i, T_a, T_e)$ 
16:   $T_s \leftarrow dT_s$  ◁ Update with new values
17:   $T_h \leftarrow dT_h$ 
18:   $T_i \leftarrow dT_i$ 
19:   $T_e \leftarrow dT_e$ 
20:   $\text{save\_results}()$ 
21: end for

```

The **REST application** service is the final and optional component to externally interact with the simulator engine. The goal is to create a confidential training workbench to allow third parties to obtain reliable simulated data while the knowledge of the model equations is preserved. Thus, the REST application service isolates the model equations and, at the same time, acts as direct access to the data generated by the simulation engine. The reason for creating a confidential training workbench is that some thermal formulas need to be protected due to closed-source licensing reasons. For example, there are HVAC manufacturers that provide closed-source model formulas to emulate the operational states of their systems to evaluate them in certain scenarios. In the present article, the developed REST API receives a one-hot vector array according to the available actions described in [Section 3.3](#).

An endpoint called *train* is coded to show how the simulation engine can be used. [Table 1](#) depicts an example of a JSON³ code data to send to the API. The *action* vector contains the actions taken in each time step to control the active element of the building (ACT_{HP}). The *datetime_start* contains the initial simulation date. The *datetime_end* contains the final simulation date. Finally, the *simulation_steps* value defines the Δ time gap value to calculate the total simulated time steps.

[Table 2](#) shows an example of data received from the API. If a simulation can be run successfully (the send values are correct and valid), the API will return a large JSON array containing the results of each sent action. In this example, the data depicted in [Figure 2](#) was sent and it returned to the global horizontal irradiation, date, T_a , and T_s values. As illustrated, every 10 s, a JSON entry is added to the resulting JSON array showing how the simulator environment values are changing according to the control formulas applied and the actions sent to the active element.

³ https://www.w3schools.com/whatis/whatis_json.asp.

Table 1. *JSON needed to send the data to the simulation environment*

Variable name	Type	Example values	Description
action	Vector	[0, 1, 0, ...]	Contains an integer vector that represents the actions taken in each time step to control the active element of the building
datetime_start	Date	2019-01-01	Initial simulation date in date format. It represents when the user wants to start the simulation process
datetime_end	Date	2019-04-23	Final simulation date in date format. It represents when the user wants to end the simulation process
simulation_steps	Integer	60	An integer value that represents the Δ time gap value to calculate the total simulated time steps

Table 2. *JSON data received by the API*

Variable name	Type	Example values	Description
GHI	Float	0.0	Global horizontal irradiance values understanding the relationship between temperatures and irradiance.
date	Datetime with time zone	2019-01-01 00:00:10 + 00:00	Full datetime with time zone.
t_a	Float	7.4	Ambient temperature from exogenous data.
t_i	Float	19.9997	Interior temperature from the model.
t_s	Float	19.9999	Sensor temperature from the model.

4.2. Used technical tools

The architecture depicted in Section 4.1 is implemented using different technical tools and libraries. The Python programming language⁴ is used as the backbone of the implementation. It allows for easy readability of the programmed code to developers who do not have a broad experience in hard-type languages (e.g., Java or C) and contains several powerful Data Science libraries for doing AI research. The Nginx reverse web/proxy server⁵ is used to manage the API requests, perform the required redirections to call the API instances, and manage the data transactions. The Ubuntu⁶ operating system is used because it is free, easy to use, and allows for a custom compilation of different data science libraries.

To be able to run the API, several technical libraries are used. Flask is a micro-framework that allows the creation of web services using a few code lines. In this implementation, it is used to create the REST application service. Flask-Security and Itsdangerous libraries are used to extend Flask's capabilities by adding an extra security layer to web services, such as signed tokens, reCAPTCHA,⁷ and email sending when there is an error in the web service. Gunicorn is a Web Server Gateway Interface⁸ server designed to forward requests from external sources to web application services, or frameworks written in Python. In

⁴ <https://www.python.org/>.

⁵ <https://www.nginx.com/>.

⁶ <https://ubuntu.com/>.

⁷ <https://www.google.com/recaptcha/about/>.

⁸ <https://www.python.org/dev/peps/pep-0333/>.

Table 3. Performance escalation results of the simulation environment

N.Years	CPU (%)	Memory (MB)	E.Time (Min)
1	39.5	224.82	5.07
2	40.4	398.31	10.08
3	39.8	517.02	17.02
4	39.0	705.51	21.89

this implementation, Gunicorn creates an internal Linux socket to pass the information to the Nginx reverse proxy server: the idea is that Nginx handles the connections and uses the internal socket as a middle communication between the end users and the Gunicorn web server. Jschema is a Python implementation for JSON schema vocabulary.⁹ It is used to validate the data sent by the end users to ensure that the requests contain reliable and valid data. Finally, the Arrow library enhances the usage of dates and times in Python, allowing easy management of different times, especially when there is an interest of handling time zones.

5. Validation

The presented training workbench is validated using two different methodologies: (1) a technical validation to study the impact of the model on the resources of a machine; and (2) a model validation to verify that results from the model are accurate and agree with the results of validated models.

5.1. Technical validation

Technical validation is aimed at validating whether the developed workbench can be used on a regular machine and escalated onto different systems. In this article, the authors used a laptop computer based on an INTEL CORE CPU 9850H, with 6 cores and 12 logical processors, 64 GB of RAM memory DDR4, and 1 T Solid State Drive GEN 3 inside an M.2 factor connection. The central processing unit (CPU), memory, and execution time values were analyzed using the *psutil*¹⁰ Python library, which allows obtaining information about the running processes and system utilization. The technical validation was conducted using two different approaches: (1) a cumulative simulation and (2) an individual simulation. In both cases, the training workbench was fed with weather and electrical prices datasets, from 2016 to 2019.

5.1.1. Cumulative simulation

The cumulative simulation performs a continuous annual simulation to stress the machine capacity of storing the given values into memory and study the impact of a continuous, long training procedure. The aim is to study the suitability of the developed workbench to be escalated when several years of external datasets are given.

The simulation starts by only simulating the impact of 1-year data and is escalated to simulate a total of 4 years. On each execution, the CPU, memory, and elapsed time parameters are tracked. Table 3 depicts the results of the test; the column *N.Years* contains the total continuous simulated years, the column *CPU* contains the used mean CPU percentage, the column *Memory* contains the mean memory consumption in MB, and the column *E.Time* contains the elapsed time in minutes.

As observed in the given results, CPU usage remains similar in each test and is within logical values considering that the target machine is not an enterprise-grade machine (e.g., a server with an Intel Xeon family processor).

⁹<https://json-schema.org/>.

¹⁰<https://github.com/giampaolo/psutil>.

Table 4. Individual results of the simulation environment

Year	CPU (%)	Memory (MB)	E.Time (Min)
2016	42.5	264.62	5.20
2017	41.2	295.23	4.77
2018	42.5	261.18	5.24
2019	40.6	299.86	4.97

Memory consumption grows as more yearly data are processed and stored in memory. The values obtained are reasonable, considering that a consumer-grade computer has 16 GB of RAM memory. Surprisingly, the memory consumption is not linear among the different tests; for example, the difference between the 2- and 1-year simulations is 173.49 MB, whereas the difference between the 3- and 2-year simulations is 118.71 MB. This is because the provided external weather and electricity price datasets contain different values and have a direct impact on the internal equations exposed in [Section 3](#).

The execution time for each year is around 5 min. In terms of real usage, this is again reasonable considering the complexity of the designed equations.

5.1.2. Individual simulation

The individual simulation simulates the required resources to simulate one specific year. The test analyses the variation of the required resources among different years to study the variations of the computer resources. [Table 4](#) reveals the results obtained by the validation procedure.

Results reveal a reasonable similarity between different years. The leap year (2016) is not the most demanding one, which confirms that the use of machine resources is more linked to the requirements of the target equations to compute the data given by the external datasets.

5.2. Model validation

The simulation engine has been validated regarding its physical performance. This has been done by means of a definition of test sequences, where backward identification of its fundamental engineering parameters has been performed. Tests regarding steady state (thermal resistance and solar heat gain) and transient (time constants) performance of the building and heat pump (coefficient of performance) have been conducted as follows:

- **Experiment 1.** Steady state 20 to 0 °C indoor–outdoor temperature difference without solar radiation. The overall thermal resistance of the building is compared with Bacher and Madsen (2011) with an accuracy of 1%.
- **Experiment 2.** Steady state 20 to 0 °C indoor–outdoor temperature difference with 300 W/m^2 of incident solar radiation. The overall gA value of the wall of the building is compared with Bacher and Madsen (2011) with an accuracy of 0.3%.
- **Experiment 3.** Stepwise 20/0 °C variation of indoor temperature with 0 °C outdoor temperature and no solar radiation. The longest time constant of the building is compared with Bacher and Madsen (2011) with accuracy better than 0.1 h.
- **Experiment 4.** Transient outdoor temperature. The coefficient of performance of the heat pump is compared with De Coninck and Helsens (2016) with an accuracy better than 2%. This value is better than the resolution provided for this parameter in standardized rating processes (only one decimal figure).

6. Discussion

In this work, a building energy performance simulator based on simplified equations from engineering and GB models is developed, integrated with occupancy models and weather forecasting files into a

Table 5. Comparison of different solutions versus the presented contribution

Name	Model	Backend	Resource	Complexity	Adjustable
Sinergym ¹¹	WB	Yes	High	High	Hard
ALFALFA ¹²	WB	Yes	High	High	Hard
BOPTEST ¹³	WB	No	Medium	High	Hard
ACTB ¹⁴	WB	Yes	High	High	Hard
Talib et al. (2023)	GB	No	Medium	Medium	Medium
Kumar et al. (2023)	GB	No	Medium	Medium	Medium
Abtahi et al. (2024)	GB	No	Medium	Medium	Medium
Gokhale et al. (2022)	GB	No	Medium	Medium	Medium
Knudsen et al. (2021)	BB	No	Low	Low	Easy
Lin et al. (2022)	BB	Yes	Low	Medium	Easy
Kamel et al. (2020)	BB	No	Low	Low	Easy
Mugnini et al. (2020)	BB	No	Low	Low	Easy
Ours	GB	No	Low	Low	Easy

unified implementation with the capacity for a rapid modification of simplified equations to fit the simulation to the required environment and building conditions.

As stated in Section 2, the integration of intelligent control-oriented solutions with building energy simulations is a challenging task, implying expertise in various domains (engineering, data science, algorithms creation, programming, software integration, etc.). Having an excellent implementation of building energy simulation is of utmost relevance to ensure that control-oriented solutions are developed against the most accurate “reality” in a virtual environment, and that all possible use cases are covered.

The proposed solution introduces an integrated simulation tool that encompasses all necessary software modules, serving as a comprehensive training and testing workbench for simulating building energy performance, HVAC systems, and user behavior. This tool is implemented as standalone software, which can be executed remotely via the built-in RESTful API system. This functionality empowers end users to develop control-oriented solutions within any software environment and programming language. Consequently, users aiming to develop machine ML-based solutions can seamlessly connect their development processes with the simulation tool through the API system, thereby facilitating the integration, training, and testing of their algorithms.

The approach can be adapted to different buildings and user behaviors by adapting its parameters. Additional complexities could be added to the HVAC system by developing adaptations of the current model (see the proposed model extensions in Section 7.2).

This is a substantial progress over existing solutions, where either complex integration is required, or the accuracy of the physical phenomena is limited.

Table 5 depicts a description of the features of the presented solution and other existing solutions for the integration of control-oriented solutions with building energy performance simulators. Here, the type of thermal “model” (WB, GB, and BB), the need to use an external third-party software as “backend,” the need for computational “resources,” the “complexity” to integrate the proposed solution in a custom development, and how “adjustable” the solution is to different scenarios (e.g., other buildings) are stated.

As illustrated in the table, the proposed solution distinguishes itself from existing approaches across several parameters. First, the employed model is an RC-Model (GB), which facilitates the generation of

¹¹ <https://github.com/ugr-sail/sinergym>.

¹² <https://github.com/NREL/alfalfa/wiki>.

¹³ <https://ibpsa.github.io/project1-boptest/>.

¹⁴ <https://github.com/henze-research-group/MODRLC>.

extensive building data. This model can accommodate unexpected scenarios, such as pandemic outbreaks or unusual weather conditions, which other models may not handle effectively. Furthermore, it can adapt to future modifications in the building, such as the installation of a new façade or the replacement of windows, thereby enabling the analysis of how these changes impact the data. Second, the proposed solution obviates the need for third-party (backend) software, thereby reducing computational expenses associated with model loading and usage. Third, the technical design and implementation of the system are relatively straightforward, requiring minimal resources. Fourth, the implementation complexity is low, as it necessitates the modification of only a single file (the RC-model formulas). Finally, as previously mentioned, the adjustment of the model is relatively simple, requiring only alterations to the implicit formulas of the RC model.

Nonetheless, the presented work has its own limitations: (1) The necessity for thermal experts to create, calibrate, and formulate the model equations remains, which hinders the widespread adoption of this approach among technical profiles lacking substantial experience in thermal modeling. (2) The RC models require periodic updates and calibration to reflect the most current building changes. Although there are studies attempting to automate the re-adaptation of these models, this remains an open challenge. (3) Real data are essential for model calibration, similar to other modeling approaches, where the reliance on real data persists.

7. Future work

The technical work presented in this article consists of a novel approach to allow the creation of intelligent control-oriented solutions following a comprehensive architecture. However, despite having the required technical tools to effectively train different solutions based on ML, different improvements can be applied in order to further enhance their functionalities.

7.1. Technical extensions

The current implementation would benefit from the following technical extensions regarding security and usability:

- The addition of more security measures and endpoints to enhance the experience of the REST application service.
- The development of alternative interaction procedures for the training of control-oriented solutions. The current implementation only defines a single procedure for training ML algorithms through a direct interaction between the researcher's inputs and the simulation engine. In this regard, the ability to make modifications to the simulation engine itself by providing, for example, a custom weather file or custom electricity prices will definitely enhance the training experience. This modification allows the researcher to use the model as a base archetype for training more generalized algorithms and adapting to a defined location. In addition, adding more endpoints allows us to define the granularity of the data to be extracted from the simulator.
- The addition of a graphical interface to allow direct modification of the simulation equations and parameters. This is largely linked to the potentialities for model extensions stated in [Section 7.2](#).

7.2. Model extension and escalation

The current work proves the feasibility of extending a thermal model of an unoccupied building into a comprehensive model comprising occupancy, ventilation, and heating appliances. However, further extensions are required to match the complexities of real-world buildings and thermal interactions:

- The thermal model of the building is limited by its mono-zonal and thermal-only approach. Extensions of the model for multi-zonal contexts could be considered.

- Advanced controls for building energy systems would potentially require better modeling of comfort in line with the requirements of the (Fanger, 1970) model, comprising at least a humidity parameter.
- The modeling of building occupants is currently limited to their presence and a quite simple induced heat load model. Their impact on the building configuration (i.e., opening of windows, activation of shading systems, etc.) and variable heat loads (i.e., separate load patterns for meetings, computer use, rest, etc.) could substantially improve the model.
- With regard to technical systems, the inclusion of more complex ventilation systems (e.g., mechanical ventilation with heat recovery and bypass), various heat diffusion systems (e.g., fan-coils and radiant surfaces) and heat production systems (i.e., solar thermal, geothermal, and boilers) could be considered.
- The present model does not allow for cooling applications. Such an extension would probably require modifications to the technical systems (e.g., mechanical chillers) and to the building model (e.g., incorporation of a humidity model and dew point calculations)
- The current model requires explicit model definition. In the current implementation, models such as Bacher and Madsen (2011) are proposed. Recent works, such as Leprince et al. (2022a), developed a generalized approach to the calibration of RC models, ultimately resulting in datasets of calibrated RC models in Leprince et al. (2022b). Thus, an interesting extension of the presented work would be to perform a specific instance of an RC model and adjust its equation parameters using the given values of their datasets.

The simulator represents the transient behavior of a building in a reduced set of equations, which makes it suitable to be escalated to larger multi-zone buildings (more complex models) or aggregated (many models running in parallel) into district-scale simulators. All this considers the need for the integration of the corresponding HVAC equations. Considering the relatively small number of equations (substantially lower than for WB and BB models) should allow for efficient computation time, enabling research in intelligent energy operators delivering specific actions to each zone.

8. Conclusion

A model is compiled based on well-referenced sources for the realistic simulation of indoor climate, heat loads, heating costs, and occupant estimation of a building. It is based on a calibrated building physics model of an office building in Denmark, which is extended with ventilation, heat production, and heat distribution equations of a typical HVAC appliances in such buildings. Model equations have been successfully adapted from various original sources into a full simulation model. This produces an interesting framework where this approach can be adopted for other building models, considering also multi-zone buildings, and inclusion of other heating, ventilation, and air conditioning systems, such as cooling appliances, heat recovery systems, and other heat production systems.

The benefit for researchers is the creation of an integration tool to test and develop their control-oriented solutions, allowing them to scale their systems and create embedded applications to be deployed in the target building control system. In addition, no specific knowledge about thermal simulations is required, as it is only necessary to implement direct equations to calculate the transition dynamics of the target building. The presented framework takes into account the external disturbances that are exogenous variables that affect to the dynamics of the building by giving the required modules to load, a set of files to emulate the location and building usage of the target environment.

Data availability statement. The code of this study is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15303664> (rubenmulero 2025).

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Ethical standard. The research meets all ethical guidelines, including adherence to the legal requirements of the study country.

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Appendix A

In Section 3, a set of different thermal equations are presented with the aim of explaining the proposed thermal model for the simulation engine. Table A1 depicts the nomenclature used and parameters to understand the exposed equations.

Table A1. Nomenclature and parameters used in the model formulas exposed in thermal model presentation

Item	Description	Units	Value
ACT_h	Activation signal for the heating system	Boolean	Variable
ACT_{Vent}	Activation signal for the ventilation System	Boolean	Variable
A_e	Effective window area of the building ^a	m^2	3.87
A_w	Effective radiation area of building envelope ^a	m^2	5.75
C_e	Thermal capacity of the building envelope ^a	$kW h/K$	3.32
C_h	Thermal capacity of the heating system ^a	$kW h/K$	0.889
C_i	Thermal capacity of the indoor space ^a	$kW h/K$	0.0928
C_s	Thermal capacity of the sensor ^a	$kW h/K$	0.0549
COP	Coefficient of performance of the heat pump ^b	-	Variable
$Fihg$	Specific internal heat load factor ^c	$W/per s$	117, 81
I_s	Solar irradiation on the horizontal plane ^a	W/m^2	Input
n	Radiator exponent ^d	-	1.33
Ocup	Presence of occupants in the building ^c	Pers	Variable
Ph_{el}	Electric consumption of the heating system	W	Variable
$Q_{boost,max}$	Maximum heat delivery capacity of the in-line electric heater	W	3000
Q_h	Heat delivered by the heating system	W	Variable
$Q_{h,boost}$	Heat delivered by the in-line electric heater	W	Variable
$Q_{h,hP}$	Heat delivered by the heat pump	W	Variable
$Q_{h,nom}$	Nominal heat delivery capacity of the heating system ^a	W	9,000
$Q_{hp,max}$	Maximum heat delivery capacity of the heat pump	W	5,000
$Q_{h,min}$	Minimum heat delivery capacity of the heat pump	W	1,000
Q_{ig}	Internal heat gains	W	Variable
Q_{vent}	Ventilation heat load ^f	kW	Variable
Rea	TR ^g between the building envelope and the outdoor ambient ^a	K/kW	4.38
Rie	TR ^g between the building envelope and the indoor space ^a	K/kW	0.897
Rih	TR ^g between the heating system and the indoor space ^a	K/kW	0.146
R_s	TR ^f between the sensor and the indoor space ^a	K/kW	1.89
R_{vent}	TR ^f between the indoor and outdoor ambient due to ventilation	K/kW	Variable
T_a	Outdoor ambient temperature	$^{\circ}C$	Input
T_e	Hidden state associated to the TM ^h of the building envelope.	$^{\circ}C$	Variable
T_h	Temperature of the terminals of the heating system	$^{\circ}C$	Variable
T_i	Indoor temperature	$^{\circ}C$	Variable
$T_{i,design}$	Design indoor temperature	$^{\circ}C$	20
T_s	Temperature of the sensor	$^{\circ}C$	Variable

Continued

Table A1. *Continued*

Item	Description	Units	Value
<i>Tsup, design</i>	Design supply temperature of the heating system	°C	50
<i>Tsup, efect</i>	Effective supply temperature of the heating system	°C	Variable
<i>Tsup, set</i>	Supply temperature set by the control system	°C	Variable
<i>Vvent</i>	Ventilation flow rate ^f	m ³ /s	Variable

^aBacher and Madsen (2011).

^bDe Coninck and Helsen (2016).

^cASHRAE, American Society of Heating Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (2017).

^dTruschel (2002).

^ePage et al. (2008).

^f*Ventilation for acceptable indoor air quality* (2015).

^gThermal resistance.

^hThermal resistance.